

IMPACT OF BURNOUT ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF DOCTORS: AN EVIDENCE FROM MUZAFFARGARH DISTRICT, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Objective: World health organization recognized burnout as an occupational issue and highlighting its significance as a global health concern. Conducting research on this topic can raise awareness among healthcare professionals, policymakers, and the public about the challenges doctors face and the importance of prioritizing their mental health. The aim of this study is to explore the relation of burnout with psychological well-being in Muzaffargarh District

Methodology: A sample from 200 MBBS doctors using simple random sampling technique were taken from Muzaffargarh district. Assessment was carried out by standardized questionnaires of Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) (23-item scale), and Ryff psychological well-being scale (18-item scale). Frequency distribution was used to find the characteristics of the respondents. Chi-square test was used to measure the associations. Linear regression model were used to measure the relationship between burnout and psychological well-being.

Results: The result shows that there are 66% female and 34% male with an average age 28.1±6.45 years. The outcome of the study shows that the burnout is significantly negatively related with psychological well-being.

Conclusion: These findings highlight the need for interventions and support systems that address burnout, promote psychological well-being, and create a healthier work environment for doctors.

INTRODUCTION

Burnout is a well-recognized psychological syndrome that affects individuals across various professions, and it has garnered significant attention within the healthcare sector, particularly among doctors. Burnout is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, leading to a

sense of disillusionment and a decline in overall well-being. (Maslach, 1981) The demanding and high-stress nature of medical practice, coupled with long working hours, heavy workload, and emotional involvement in patient care, make doctors particularly susceptible to experiencing burnout. (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). The concept of burnout was first introduced in the early 1970s

by psychologists Herbert Freudenberger and Christina Maslach. Freudenberger, a psychologist and psychoanalyst, initially coined the term "burnout" to describe the emotional and physical exhaustion he observed among his colleagues working in a drug rehabilitation center. In 1974, (Freudenberger, 1974). Christina Maslach, a social psychologist, expanded on the concept and developed the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), a widely used and validated instrument for measuring burnout in various occupational settings, including healthcare (Maslach, 1981). Over the years, burnout research has gained momentum, with numerous studies investigating its prevalence, causes, and consequences among doctors. In the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11), the World Health Organization (WHO) recognized burnout as an occupational issue and highlighting its significance as a global health concern (World Health Organization, 2019).

Burnout is defined as an emotional and physical condition of exhaustion. It can occur if you are constantly stressed at work or have spent a long time in a physically or emotionally demanding position. You become less productive and less energetic as a result of burnout, which also makes you feel more hopeless, cynical, and resentful. You can eventually feel as though you have nothing more to contribute. Burnout, a persistent state of physical and emotional depletion caused by excessive work or personal expectations, or continual stress, is a symptom of emotional exhaustion (Wright, 1998). It refers to the sensation of being emotionally overburdened and weary by one's labor. Physical exhaustion and a sense of being psychologically and emotionally "drained" are symptoms (Zohar, 1997)

The term "psychological well-being" refers to a person's mental health and general functioning. Psychological well-being is defined by the author of a study published in *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being* as "functioning effectively and the combination of feeling good." Huppert & Felici, (2009). Psychological wellbeing (PWB) is quite similar to other terms that refer to positive mental states, such as happiness or satisfaction, and in many ways, they are interchangeable,

worrying about fine distinctions. There are two fundamental aspects to psychological well-being. The first refers to how much people experience good emotions and sentiments of happiness. Subjective well-being is another term for this component of psychological well-being (Diener, 2000). The phrase "Hedonic" well-being usually refers to subjective sensations of happiness. It is made up of two parts: a cognitive component (life satisfaction) and an affective component (high positive affect and low negative affect). According to Carruthers and Hood (2004), a person experiences happiness when both positive affect and life satisfaction are high. The purposive part of PWB is referred to as "Eudemonic" well-being. Carol Ryff, a psychologist, has established a very clear model that divides Eudemonic wellness into six basic forms of psychological wellbeing.

According to Seifert (2005) The Ryff Psychological Well-Being scale consist of: **Self-acceptance:** A high score suggests that the respondent has a positive attitude towards himself or herself. **Environmental mastery:** A high score shows that the respondent makes good use of opportunities and has a sense of mastery over environmental components and activities such as managing everyday affairs and establishing settings that support personal needs. **Positive interpersonal interactions:** A high score indicates that the responder is involved in significant interpersonal relationships, such as reciprocal empathy, sensitivity, and compassion. **Personal development:** High scores indicate that the person is still growing, is open to new experiences, and recognizes changes in behavior and self through time. **Life Purpose:** High scores suggest that the respondent has a strong goal orientation and believes that life has meaning. **Autonomy:** A high score suggests that the respondent is self-sufficient and controls his or her own behavior regardless of societal influences (Seifert, 2005). According to Teoh et al., (2023) perceived working conditions (i.e., job demands, job resource), psychological well-being (i.e., emotional exhaustion, work engagement), and patient care (i.e., clinical care, patient safety) findings emphasize the need of approaching working conditions from a systems

perspective in order to improve both doctors' psychological well-being and patient care.

Balhatchet et al., (2023) Burnout and/or wellness (job demands) were influenced by the following factors: working hours and workload; the work and learning environment; inappropriate behavior; and examination and academic stress of Doctors. Gagnon et al., (2016) demonstrates that self-regulation capacity is fundamental self-help skill and they found through research that self-regulation capacity predicted psychological well-being and less burnout. According to Patel et al., (2018) physicians face daily challenges in providing care to their patients, and burnout may result from elevated stress levels among overworked doctors. Farrell et al., (2019) supports in literature that government and medical institution should optimize the well-being of medical students. Kareaga et al., (2009) states in their research that Burnout was found to be negatively associated to psychological well-being. Burnout also predicts unfavorable results on numerous levels (physical, psychological, professional, family, and social). Van Hoy & Rzeszutek,(2022) stated in their research of systematic view of existing research burnout and well-being of psychotherapists are related to socio-demographic variables, interpersonal and work related factors. Yu & Chae, (2020) also reported that burnout negatively correlated with psychological well-being of medical students. Male cynism score was higher than female students. A study of Tabur et al., (2022) evidencing that Anxiety, burnout, and sadness were among the emotions experienced by doctors and nurses/mid wives, technician and healthcare workers impacting negatively on psychological well-being and health drove attention to quit their job. Rehman et al., (2020) proposed that with the help of social support psychological well-being increases and burnout decreases. West et al., (2018) reports Individual physician traits also have a role, with female and younger physicians suffering from burnout at a higher incidence.

Maslach's Theory of Burnout

According to Maslach (2003) One of the most widely recognized theories of burnout, proposed

by Christina Maslach, identifies three key dimensions: Emotional fatigue, depersonalization, and a decrease in personal accomplishment are all symptoms of depression. Emotional tiredness is characterized by sensations of being emotionally spent and drained. The intense and demanding nature of medical practice, including long working hours, high patient volumes, and emotional involvement in patient care, can gradually wear down doctors' resilience. Depersonalization involves developing a cynical and detached attitude toward patients or work. The continuous exposure to suffering, the pressure to deliver optimal care, and the burden of managing administrative tasks can erode empathy and compassion. Reduced personal accomplishment refers to a diminished sense of competence and achievement. This feeling of ineffectiveness can be demoralizing and lead to decreased job satisfaction and motivation.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study examine the relationship between burnout levels and psychological well-being among doctors belongs sanctioned in Muzaffargarh District.

Study Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There will be a significant relationship between burnout and the psychological well-being of doctors.

Hypothesis 2: There will be a negative relation between burnout levels and the psychological well-being of doctors. Higher levels of burnout will be associated with lower levels of psychological well-being.

Methodology

Sampling and Sampling Design

A total of approximately 500 MBBS doctors are sanctioned in Muzaffargarh district. By using a sample size calculator (<http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>) using margin of error 5.3% with a confidence level 90% the recommended sample size was 163. A sample from 200 MBBS doctors using simple random sampling technique were collected from

Muzaffargarh district. Respondents who refused to respond were excluded and a new sample was generated. Participants from Muzaffargarh district has registered MBBS degree were considered.

Instruments

The instruments include standardized questionnaires, such as the Maslach Burnout

Inventory (MBI) (23-item scale) for Burnout, and Ryff psychological well-being scale (18-item scale) for measuring psychological well-being. The measure the reliability of this well-defined scale we use reliability analysis, and the results are presented in table 1.

Table 1 Reliability of Scale

	Mean	SD	Cronbach alpha [95% CI]
Burnout	3.107	0.657	0.782 [0.736 - 0.823]
Psychological well-being	4.760	1.076	0.671 [0.601 - 0.734]

Table 1 shows the results of the reliability of the Burnout and Psychological Well-being Scale. As the values of Cronbach alpha are above 60% thus the questionnaire is reliable to use.

Research Design

Research examines the relationship between variables without manipulating them. Research framework was quantitative in nature. Researchers typically use self-report measures to assess burnout and psychological well-being in doctors.

Ethical Considerations

This study was a semester project of the first authors and conducted by keeping in view all ethical considerations of international standards. Moreover, informed consent was taken from participants in written form. Participants were told

that their participation is voluntary, and they can withdraw anytime if they feel any inconvenience.

Statistical Analysis

Frequency distribution was used to find the characteristics of the respondents. Chi-square test was used to measure the associations. Linear regression model were used to measure the relationship between burnout and psychological well-being.

Results

Table 2 presents the results of the frequency analysis. Result shows that out of 200 respondent 136 females and 68 males. Average age of the MBBS doctors was 28. Married respond more than unmarried.

Table 2 Frequency Analysis

Variable	Categories	N(%)
Gender	Female	132(66%)
	Male	68(34%)
Age*		28.1(6.45)
Marital Status	Married	103(51.5%)
	Unmarried	97(48.5%)
No. of Siblings*		3.81(1.68)
works in sector	Government	100(50%)
	Private	84(42%)
	Semi-Government	16(8%)
No. of working hours*		8.5(2.89)
Family system	Joint	94(47%)
	Nuclear	106(53%)

Socioeconomic Status	Lower	4(2%)
	Middle	180(90%)
	Upper	16(8%)

*Continuous variables are presented as: Mean (S.D)

Participants' working in Government sector are more than private and semi-Government. Average working hours are 8.5, mostly Participants live in nuclear family system than joint. 90% participants belongs to Middle class in socioeconomic status.

Table 3 Association of Burnout with Gender in MBBS Doctors

Items	Female							Male							p-value
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
I feel emotionally exhausted because of my work	10 (7.5 8%)	20(1 5.15 %)	23(1 7.42 %)	32(2 4.24 %)	23(1 7.42 %)	12(9 .09 %)	12(9 .09 %)	8(11 .76 %)	8(11 .76 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	6(8.))	10(1 4.71 %)	4(5.))	0. 39 4
I feel worn out at the end of a working day	12(9 .09 %)	7(5. 3%)	36(2 7.27 %)	19(1 4.39 %)	6(4.))	32(2 4.24 %)	20(1 5.15 %)	6(8.))	10(1 4.71 %)	6(8.))	32(4 7.06 %)	4(5.))	6(8.))	4(5.))	.0 00 *
I feel tired as soon as I get up in the morning and see a new working day stretched out in front of me	25(1 8.94 %)	15(1 1.36 %)	26(1 9.7 %)	16(1 2.12 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	6(8.))	10(1 4.71 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	2(2.))	6(8.))	12(1 7.65 %)	0. 06 2
I can easily understand the actions of my colleagues/supervisors	6(4. 55%)	10(7 .58 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	20(1 5.15 %)	11(8 .33 %)	16(1 2.12 %)	51(3 8.64 %)	4(5.))	4(5.))	4(5.))	6(8.))	10(1 4.71 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	30(4 4.12 %)	0. 37 2
I get the feeling that I treat some clients/colleagues impersonally, as if they were objects	58(4 3.94 %)	23(1 7.42 %)	10(7 .58 %)	20(1 5.15 %)	15(1 1.36 %)	6(4.))	55% 0(0 %)	22(3 2.35 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	2(2.))	2(2.))	6(8.))	6(8.))	.0 00 *,b
Working with people the whole day is stressful for me	25(1 8.94 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	19(1 4.39 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	16(1 2.12 %)	20(2 9.41 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	4(5.))	12(1 7.65 %)	2(2.))	12(1 7.65 %)	6(8.))	0. 16 3
I deal with other people's problems successfully	2(1. 52%)	16(1 2.12 %)	8(6. 06%)	12(9 .09 %)	12(9 .09 %)	48(3 6.36 %)	34(2 5.76 %)	0(0 %)	2(2.))	6(8.))	14(2 0.59 %)	6(8.))	14(2 0.59 %)	26(3 8.24 %)	.0 13 *,b,c
I feel burned out because of my work	19(1 4.39 %)	25(1 8.94 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	12(9 .09 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	26(1 9.7 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	8(11 .76 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	6(8.))	14(2 0.59 %)	4(5.))	0. 57 0
I feel that I influence other people positively through my work	8(6. 06%)	16(1 2.12 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	23(1 7.42 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	31(2 3.48 %)	2(2.))	14(2 0.59 %)	6(8.))	6(8.))	4(5.))	12(1 7.65 %)	24(3 5.29 %)	0. 14 3
I have become more callous to people since I have started doing this job	24(1 8.18 %)	29(2 1.97 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	10(7 .58 %)	12(9 .09 %)	17(1 2.88 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	4(5.))	6(8.))	8(11 .76 %)	0. 06 1

I'm afraid that my work makes me emotionally harder	27(2 0.45)	12(9 .09)	20(1 5.15)	18(1 3.64)	19(1 4.39)	14(1 0.61)	22(1 6.67)	18(2 6.47)	8(11 .76)	14(2 0.59)	8(11 .76)	8(11 .76)	8(11 .76)	4(5.)	0. 39 6
I feel full of energy	18(1 3.64)	8(6. 06%)	8(6. 06%)	19(1 4.39)	14(1 0.61)	32(2 4.24 5%)	33(2 5%)	6(8.)	2(2.)	4(5.)	24(3 5.29)	12(1 7.65)	4(5.)	16(2 3.53)	.0 02 *
I feel frustrated by my work	18(1 3.64)	26(1 9.7)	20(1 5.15)	18(1 3.64)	17(1 2.88)	16(1 2.12)	17(1 2.88)	12(1 7.65)	10(1 4.71)	6(8.)	12(1 7.65)	14(2 0.59)	10(1 4.71)	4(5.)	0. 32 0
I get the feeling that I work too hard	12(9 .09)	10(7 .58)	23(1 7.42)	12(9 .09)	8(6. 06%)	24(1 8.18)	43(3 2.58)	4(5.)	8(11 .76)	12(1 7.65)	8(11 .76)	6(8.)	10(1 4.71)	20(2 9.41)	0. 84 2
I'm not really interested in what is going on with many of my colleagues	33(2 5%)	16(1 2.12)	12(9 .09)	14(1 0.61)	9(6. 82%)	18(1 3.64)	30(2 2.73)	14(2 0.59)	4(5.)	8(11 .76)	16(2 3.53)	4(5.)	16(2 3.53)	6(8.)	.0 21 *
Being in direct contact with people at work is too stressful	23(1 7.42)	10(7 .58)	28(2 1.21)	24(1 8.18)	15(1 1.36)	12(9 .09)	20(1 5.15)	8(11 .76)	8(11 .76)	12(1 7.65)	14(2 0.59)	12(1 7.65)	4(5.)	10(1 4.71)	0. 66 0
I find it easy to build a relaxed atmosphere in my working environment	12(9 .09)	13(9 .85)	14(1 0.61)	22(1 6.67)	8(6. 06%)	26(1 9.7)	37(2 8.03)	6(8.)	4(5.)	10(1 4.71)	14(2 0.59)	10(1 4.71)	6(8.)	18(2 6.47)	0. 17 8
I feel stimulated when I been working closely with my colleagues	12(9 .09)	12(9 .09)	19(1 4.39)	12(9 .09)	8(6. 06%)	32(2 4.24)	37(2 8.03)	4(5.)	10(1 4.71)	10(1 4.71)	16(2 3.53)	0(0)	8(11 .76)	20(2 9.41)	.0 13 *
I feel stimulated when I been working closely with my colleagues	8(6. 06%)	21(1 5.91)	16(1 2.12)	10(7 .58)	12(9 .09)	30(2 2.73)	35(2 6.52)	4(5.)	4(5.)	16(2 3.53)	12(1 7.65)	0(0)	16(2 3.53)	16(2 3.53)	.0 07 *
I have achieved many rewarding objectives in my work	26(1 9.7)	17(1 2.88)	28(2 1.21)	20(1 5.15)	17(1 2.88)	16(1 2.12)	8(6. 06%)	12(1 7.65)	10(1 4.71)	2(2.)	14(2 0.59)	8(11 .76)	16(2 3.53)	6(8.)	.0 19 *
I feel as if I'm at my wits' end	20(1 5.15)	10(7 .58)	19(1 4.39)	14(1 0.61)	33(2 5%)	26(1 9.7)	10(7 .58)	8(11 .76)	10(1 4.71)	6(8.)	14(2 0.59)	14(2 0.59)	8(11 .76)	8(11 .76)	0. 13 0

In my work I am very relaxed when dealing with emotional problems	20(1 5.15)	8(6. 06%)	30(2 2.73)	16(1 2.12)	20(1 5.15)	21(1 5.91)	17(1 2.88)	4(5. 88%)	6(8. 82%)	14(2 0.59)	12(1 7.65)	2(2. 94%)	14(2 0.59)	16(2 3.53)	.0 24 *
I have the feeling that my colleagues blame me for some of their problems	36(2 7.27)	21(1 5.91)	24(1 8.18)	19(1 4.39)	6(4. 55%)	16(1 2.12)	10(7 .58)	18(2 6.47)	24(3 5.29)	6(8. 82%)	8(11 .76)	2(2. 94%)	6(8. 82%)	4(5. 88%)	0. 08 0

The Table 3 presents the results of gender wise comparison of the items of Burnout. Table shows that only 9 items out of 23 are gender associated because they have significant p value while 14 items are not gender associated and their p value is non-significant.

Table 4 Association of Psychological Well-Being with Gender in MBBS Doctors

Items	Female							Male							p- va lu e
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
"I like most parts of my personality."	0(0)	6(4. 55)	6(4. 55)	8(6. 06)	20(1 5.15)	34(2 5.76)	58(4 3.94)	0(0)	4(5. 88)	0(0)	2(2. 94)	16(2 3.53)	26(3 8.24)	20(2 9.41)	.0 59 b
"When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out so far"	4(3. 03)	2(1. 52)	10(7 .58)	6(4. 55)	24(1 8.18)	39(2 9.55)	47(3 5.61)	0(0)	4(5. 88)	0(0)	2(2. 94)	10(1 4.71)	22(3 2.35)	30(4 4.12)	.0 71 b
"Some people wander aimlessly through life, but I am not one of them."	2(1. 52)	10(7 .58)	10(7 .58)	12(9 .09)	20(1 5.15)	19(1 4.39)	59(4 4.7)	0(0)	6(8. 82)	4(5. 88)	4(5. 88)	16(2 3.53)	14(2 0.59)	24(3 5.29)	.4 66 b,c
"The demands of everyday life often get me down."	26(1 9.7)	35(2 6.52)	28(2 1.21)	12(9 .09)	15(1 1.36)	12(9 .09)	4(3. 03)	8(11 .76)	12(1 7.65)	24(3 5.29)	10(1 4.71)	2(2. 94)	4(5. 88)	8(11 .76)	.0 06 *
"In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life."	14(1 0.61)	29(2 1.97)	10(7 .58)	12(9 .09)	16(1 2.12)	14(1 0.61)	37(2 8.03)	4(5. 88)	6(8. 82)	16(2 3.53)	12(1 7.65)	8(11 .76)	12(1 7.65)	10(1 4.71)	.0 01 *
"Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me."	32(2 4.24)	25(1 8.94)	18(1 3.64)	21(1 5.91)	14(1 0.61)	10(7 .58)	12(9 .09)	6(8. 82)	14(2 0.59)	14(2 0.59)	6(8. 82)	2(2. 94)	18(2 6.47)	8(11 .76)	.0 01 *

“I live life one day at a time and don't really think about the future.”	24(1 8.18 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	28(2 1.21 %)	6(4. 55 %)	24(1 8.18 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	8(11 .76 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	8(11 .76 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	8(11 .76 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	0. 05 1
“In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.”	3(2. 27 %)	6(4. 55 %)	4(3. 03 %)	24(1 8.18 %)	29(2 1.97 %)	36(2 7.27 %)	30(2 2.73 %)	2(2. 94 %)	8(11 .76 %)	4(5. 88 %)	8(11 .76 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	20(2 9.41 %)	.2 77 b
“I am good at managing the responsibilities of daily life.”	10(7 .58 %)	4(3. 03 %)	6(4. 55 %)	12(9 .09 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	33(2 5%)	49(3 7.12 %)	4(5. 88 %)	4(5. 88 %)	8(11 .76 %)	4(5. 88 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	24(3 5.29 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	.1 01 b
“I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life.”	27(2 0.45 %)	24(1 8.18 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	23(1 7.42 %)	12(9 .09 %)	10(7 .58 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	6(8. 82 %)	4(5. 88 %)	0. 59 2
“For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.”	5(3. 79 %)	0(0 %)	2(1. 52 %)	8(6. 06 %)	10(7 .58 %)	27(2 0.45 %)	80(6 0.61 %)	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	2(2. 94 %)	8(11 .76 %)	22(3 2.35 %)	36(5 2.94 %)	.1 35 b,c
““I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how I think about myself and the world.””	2(1. 52 %)	0(0 %)	5(3. 79 %)	10(7 .58 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	29(2 1.97 %)	72(5 4.55 %)	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	0(0 %)	6(8. 82 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	36(5 2.94 %)	.4 94 b,c
“People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.”	6(4. 55 %)	5(3. 79 %)	8(6. 06 %)	16(1 2.12 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	37(2 8.03 %)	42(3 1.82 %)	4(5. 88 %)	2(2. 94 %)	2(2. 94 %)	8(11 .76 %)	6(8. 82 %)	18(2 6.47 %)	28(4 1.18 %)	.7 89 b
“I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago”	23(1 7.42 %)	25(1 8.94 %)	20(1 5.15 %)	8(6. 06 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	12(9 .09 %)	26(1 9.7 %)	4(5. 88 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	6(8. 82 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	6(8. 82 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	16(2 3.53 %)	.0 06 *
“I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions”	42(3 1.82 %)	33(2 5%)	16(1 2.12 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	6(4. 55 %)	13(9 .85 %)	4(3. 03 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	18(2 6.47 %)	12(1 7.65 %)	2(2. 94 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	2(2. 94 %)	.0 21 *
“I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others.”	26(1 9.7 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	19(1 4.39 %)	14(1 0.61 %)	11(8 .33 %)	22(1 6.67 %)	8(11 .76 %)	8(11 .76 %)	8(11 .76 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	2(2. 94 %)	24(3 5.29 %)	8(11 .76 %)	.0 00 *
““I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are different from the way most other people think.””	0(0 %)	8(6. 06 %)	0(0 %)	17(1 2.88 %)	18(1 3.64 %)	39(2 9.55 %)	50(3 7.88 %)	6(8. 82 %)	2(2. 94 %)	4(5. 88 %)	8(11 .76 %)	10(1 4.71 %)	24(3 5.29 %)	14(2 0.59 %)	.0 00 *,b

"I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important."	6(4.55%)	6(4.55%)	4(3.03%)	14(10.61%)	22(16.67%)	27(20.45%)	53(40.15%)	4(5.88%)	4(5.88%)	8(11.76%)	8(11.76%)	6(8.33%)	20(29.41%)	18(26.47%)	.063 ^b
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The Table 4 presents the results of gender wise comparison of the items of Psychological Well-being. This table of Psychological Well-being predicts that only 8 items out of 18 are gender associated because they have significant p value while 10 items are not gender associated and their p value is non-significant.

Fig 1 Scatter Plot of Burnout and Psychological Well-being with a fitted line

The scatter plot shows that there is negative correlation between burnout and psychological well-being which means higher level of burnout will be

associated with low level of psychological well-being which accept hypothesis 2.

Table 5. Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	P-value
Constant	98.89	3.47	28.51	0.000
Burnout	-0.15	0.04	-3.41	0.001
Marital Status				
Unmarried	-2.93	1.72	-1.7	0.090
Works in sector				
Private	-2.35	1.79	-1.31	0.192
Semi-Government	3.46	3.24	1.07	0.287

Dependent variable: Psychological wellbeing

The regression results shows that burnout is significant because p value less than 0.05 and t value is greater than 1.96 which accept hypothesis 1. Burnout is negatively correlated with psychological well-being thus hypothesis 2 is accepted. Meanwhile demographic variables are non-significant and negatively associated.

Discussion

The study aimed to investigate and explore the impact of Burnout on Psychological well-being of Doctors of District Muzaffargarh. Burnout is the important factor that influences psychological well-being of Doctors. Burnout has a detrimental impact on all

aspect of life, including your home, job, and social life. The finding of a negative correlation between burnout and psychological well-being among doctors sheds light on the significant impact of burnout on their mental health and overall well-being. Burnout is a phenomenon marked by emotional weariness, depersonalization, and decreased personal success can have profound consequences on doctors' psychological state and job satisfaction. The outcome of present study showed that there is a significant relationship between Psychological Well-being and Burnout of Doctors supported by the prior study of Patel et al., (2018) and Farrell et al., (2019). According to Patel et al., (2018) physicians face daily challenges in providing care to their patients, and

burnout may result from elevated stress levels among overworked doctors. Farrell et al., (2019) supports in literature that government and medical institution should optimize the well-being of medical students. Balhatchet et al., (2023) Burnout and/or wellness (job demands) were influenced by the following factors: working hours and workload; the work and learning environment; inappropriate behavior; and examination and academic stress of Doctors. Teoh et al., (2023). perceived working conditions (i.e., job demands, job resource), psychological well-being (i.e., emotional exhaustion, work engagement), and patient care (i.e., clinical care, patient safety) findings emphasize the need of approaching working conditions from a systems perspective in order to improve both doctors' psychological well-being and patient care.

There is a negative correlation between them. The Hypothesis 2 is supported by Kareaga et al., (2009) which states that Burnout was found to be negatively associated to psychological well-being. Another research evidence supported present study hypothesis Yu & Chae, (2020) also reported that burnout negatively correlated with psychological well-being of medical students. Male cynism score was higher than female students. A study of Tabur et al., (2022) supports both hypotheses evidencing that Anxiety, burnout, and sadness were among the emotions experienced by doctors and nurses/mid wives, technician and healthcare workers impacting negatively on psychological well-being and health drove attention to quit their job. Higher the level of Psychological Well-being lower the Burnout supported by Rehman et al., (2020) proposed that with the help of social support psychological well-being increases and burnout decreases.

Conclusion:

Correlational research consistently demonstrates a negative impact of burnout on the psychological well-being of doctors. High levels of burnout among doctors are associated with lower emotional well-being, decreased job satisfaction, diminished professional fulfillment, and potential negative effects on patient care and personal relationships. These findings highlight the urgent need for interventions and support systems that address burnout, promote psychological well-being, and create a healthier work

environment for doctors. By prioritizing the well-being of doctors, we can enhance both their personal lives and patient care. This study will help us in only for the doctors' sake but also for the overall healthcare system and patient care. Limitation of the study will be the use of self-report measures may introduce response bias and common method variance, as doctors' self-perception of burnout and psychological well-being may be influenced by various factors.

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